

Analysis of the Impact of Corruption, Insecurity, Manufacturing Output and Population Growth on Standard of Living Nigerians

Mohammed Lawal Ibrahim¹; Baba Ali Ashemi²; Caleb Amos³; Mohammed Gidado Aliyu⁴; Ayuba Suleiman⁵ & Suleiman Adamu Uteh⁶

¹ Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
ibrahimruqqy@gmail.com

² Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
ashmites@gmail.com

³ Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
amoscaleby2k@gmail.com

⁴ Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
accule9@unimaid.edu.ng

⁵ Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
ayubasuleiman12@gmail.com

⁶ Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
suliemanutai@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of corruption, insecurity, manufacturing output and population growth on the standards of living of Nigerians using annual time series data from 1994-2024. Quantitative approach was employed leveraging on Autoregressive Distributive lag model which was buttressed by the Augmented Dicker Fuller test that confirms a mixed order of integration. Results from the ARDL bound test shows no long run relationship among the variables. The short run results revealed that corruption (better Corruption Perception Index Score) has a positive significant impact on Nigeria's standard of living, implying that reduced corruption enhances per capita income by USD21.78 which aligns with the institutional theory. Furthermore, Manufacturing output reveals a strong significant positive relationship with Nigeria's standard of living by increasing it with USD30.65 which is consistent with the endogenous growth theory. Conversely, insecurity and population growth show a positive and negative impact respectively but they are not statistically significant. The error correction term indicates a 35% speed of adjustment to return to equilibrium in the long run after a short-run shock,

revealing a moderate convergence. The diagnostics test confirms that the model is stable, no autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. Recommendation includes the need to strengthen anti-corruption drive and revitalising the manufacturing sector in order to achieve an inclusive growth.

Keywords: Corruption, Insecurity, Manufacturing Output, Population growth, Per Capita Income

Introduction

Globally, population growth has recorded significant trajectory across different economies and period. This has engrossed the attention of key stakeholders across the public and private sectors. As of 2011, the world population stood at 7.09 billion, while in 2016, a positive trajectory was recorded to 7.53 billion, and in 2023, it increased to 8.06 billion (World Bank, 2023a). However, studies have indicated that a positive correlation exists between population and economic growth. Among which include Akinola (2021), Sibe (2016), Buresch, Nguyen & Nguyen, (2024); Adeosun (2021); Suluk (2021). This is further reflected in the GDP values of densely populated countries like China (USD 14.72 trillion), the United States of America (USD 25.43 trillion), and India (USD 3.41 trillion) for 2024 (World Bank, 2024). Other Factors such as business environment, infrastructure, research, & development, human capital development also plays a complementary role in contributing to this economic growth.

Nigeria presents a paradox case because despite been among the top 10 most populous countries globally and the largest in Africa, approximately 225million, and GDP of about USD477 billion (United Nations, 2021), its economic performance lags. This discrepancy can be attributed governance challenges, institutional weakness, Research and development, corruption, insecurity among others. Corruption in Nigeria has spread across all the fabric of the economy. Nigeria scoring 24 out of 100 in transparency international 2022 perception index, well below the African regional average of 32 (Transparency International, 2022). Other indices such as World Bank's World Governance indicators, Ibrahim index of Africa Governance, Bertelsmann foundation transformation index 2022 attributed low score or places Nigeria at a lower end of the scale, indicating a systematic corruption (Bertelsmann foundation, 2022; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2022; World Bank, 2023b). Major drivers of this scale of corruption in Nigeria is resource curse and neo-patrimonialism.

With this condition, it has implication on the country's employment level, income equality, level of industrialisation, poverty level, output level and the state of security. The state of security of the Nigerian economy has become a worrisome taking into cognisance the rate of corruption which can further be linked to resource control. Insecurity has become the order of the day as it has spread across the six (6) geopolitical zones of the country. The North East is faced with the Boko-Haram insurgency, North Central and West is bedeviled with farmers herder's crisis and kidnapping and banditry. The South-South and South East are challenged with the militancy and activities of the independent people of Biafra (IPOB) while the in the South West, the Oduduwa people Congress activities.

Consequently, this scenario seems to have a multiplier implication, particularly on the supply side which tends to have effect on the standard of living of the people which GDP per capita serves as a measuring tool. Manufacturing output recorded upward trajectory from 2017 to 2022 implying from USD40.69 billion to USD64.90 billion but a significant decline to USD25.4 billion was recorded in 2024, marking a 15-year low. This is attributed to factors such as exchange rate volatility, high input cost, unstable power supply, insecurity among others.

On the other hand, the per capita income or GDP per capita of Nigeria over the years has been oscillating. As at 2020 the GDP per capita was USD2,019.7, which was 11.83% decline from 2019, while that of 2021 stood at USD2,017 a marginal decline of 0.12% from 2020. In 2022, the GDP per capita was USD2,139.4, which represent 6.05% increase from 2022 but a sharp decline of 25.37% was recorded in 2023 when the GDP per capita was USD1,596.6 as against year 2022 (World Bank 2023). This raises critical question about the interaction or interplay between population growth, corruption, manufacturing output and insecurity in shaping the nation's living standards.

Although, a significant amount of the literature (e.g., Grundler & Potrafke, 2019; Odi, 2014; Lawan *et al*; 2023; Enakhe, 2018; Ezeiuhou, 2021; Agogbua, Mgbatogu & Nzewi, 2022) looks at the individual effects of corruption, insecurity, manufacturing output, and population growth on macroeconomic indicators; there is a critical gap in analysing how these issues collectively affect standard of living particularly within the context of Nigeria. More so, there is a methodological and country-specific gap because the only few studies have focused on living standards (Onov, 2024; Austin-Egoole *et al* 2022) are state-specific and qualitative in nature.

Theoretical Review

Endogenous Growth Theory: The theory is associated with the works of Paul Romer (1986, 1990) and Robert (1988). Major argument of the theory is that economic growth is driven or facilitated by internal factors rather than external forces. Particularly emphasis should be placed on human capital, innovation and knowledge. The theory is cogent to the study because it creates the bench mark or foundation for manufacturing output which serves as a key variable of the study by explaining how internal industrial production and technological advancement proportionately translates to improve standard of living. However, the major shortcoming of the theory is that it is skew on research and development and education while ignoring the role of institutions particularly governance, political stability among others. This theory is reinforced in previous studies of Odi (2014) and Anugworn (2024).

Institutional Theory: The theory emerges in the late 1970s which is linked to the works of John Meyer and Brain Rowan which seeks to explore how organisations are shaped by their environment. Particularly, it focuses on how institutions such as laws, governance and enforcement shape the economic behaviour. The theory is relevant to the study because it provides the foundation to analyse whether the predictor-corruption acts as a

lubricant for inefficiencies (i.e., grease the wheels) or acts as a barrier to development which is seen as “sand the wheels.” Furthermore, the theory is key because it advocates for transparent governance and accountability because minimise uncertainty, thereby attracting investments in critical areas that will spur standard of living. The shortcoming of the theory is that it down plays the roles of geography and technology. Also, it overemphasises on rules while downplay entrepreneurship, culture and human capital. Therefore, the study applies theory triangulation because it creates a comprehensive view of the study are because the endogenous focus on production, the institutional theory explains the environment in which the production takes place. Therefore, together they are relevant in ensuring an improved standard of living.

Corruption and Living Standards

There exists a large dossier of extant literature on the nexus between corruption on economic growth, GDP and GDP per capita. The outcome of most previous findings shows a negative and positive impact relationship between the duo. Negatively, the below studies have affirmed it in many countries, including Nigeria (Odi, 2014), Indonesia (Alfada, 2019), Ghana (Forson *et al* 2015), India (Bhattacharyya & Jha, 2013), Vietnam (Anh *et al* 2016), South Africa (Olamide & Maredza, 2023), and African countries in general (d’Agostino *et al.*, 2016). Ikazaki (2014) notes that if corruption is widespread, growth rates may be negative.

Also, Stryzhak (2025) investigates whether corruption, human capital, and economic growth are causally connected in EU candidate states using annual data for nine EU candidate countries from 1996 to 2021. Findings reveals that no causality in countries such as Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, and Ukraine while causal relationship from Control of Corruption (CC) to GDP only in Moldova. However, causal links were found in other cases, such as from GDP and life expectancy to corruption control in Montenegro, Serbia and Türkiye, and from education to GDP in Moldova, Georgia and Montenegro, the study concluded that the relationship between corruption, human capital, and economic growth varies by country and is not uniform, emphasising the need for country-specific policy approaches.

In another related study, Grundler & Potrafke (2019) examines corruption and economic growth using data from 175 countries from 2012 – 2018 discovered that the cumulative long run effect of corruption on growth is that real per capita GDP decreases by 17% when the reversed CPI increased by one standard deviation. In a similar vein, Trebelsi (2024) using non-linear evidence from 65 countries, employing data from 1987 to 2021 discovered that corruption can have a positive effect on growth. That beyond an optimal threshold, both high and low corruption negatively affects economic growth but a moderate level of corruption has a marginal effect on growth. Odi (2014) in a similar study aligns that corruption in Nigeria has a negative impact on its economic growth implying that economy cannot achieve the required growth without zero tolerance to corruption. Likewise, Nazar (2014) concluded that corruption has a negative impact on GDP per capita.

Conversely, another study by Onakoya & Folorunsho (2015) while employing Johansen cointegration and vector error correction model concluded that corruption has a positive significant and long run relation between corruption and economic growth of

Nigeria. Also, Akmal *et al* (2024) investigate the complex nexus between corruption, military expenditure, and economic growth. Using panel data analysis and the Generalised Method of moments (GMM), estimation technique on data from 50 developing countries, the findings reveals that health, education, FDI, and employment contribute positively to economic growth, while military expenditure has a detrimental effect. Although, corruption sometimes exhibits a positive impact, aligning with the “grease the wheels” hypothesis. The study concludes that although corruption may offer short-term efficiency gains, long-term growth and stability require governance reforms, reduced military expenditure, and stronger investment in social sectors. Makar *et al* (2023) in a related study in Nigeria, reveals that corruption has no significant impact on growth in the short run but in the long run it exerts a significant role on economic growth, thereby revealing that there is a weak transmission effect of corruption on growth through household consumption, FDI investment, government spending, export and import in Nigeria.

Insecurity and Living Standards

On the nexus between Insecurity and living standard or GDP per capita, several studies has been conducted domestically and internationally. Enakhe (2018) conducted a diagnostic review exploring the nexus between insecurity and economic growth in Nigeria discovers that insecurity hampers economic growth by discouraging investment, increasing unemployment, and reducing government revenue, among other adverse effects. Lawan *et al* (2023) using time series data spanning from 2000 to 2020 and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, reveals that economic growth is negatively related to terrorism both in the short and long run. Similarly, like insecurity, unemployment rates were found to adversely affect growth in both short and long run. Also, Onov (2024) assessed the impact of insecurity on household standards of living in Benue State, applying qualitative approach affirmed that insecurity has a significant negative effect on household standards of living. It further identified the major causes of insecurity in the state, which include political grievances, socio-cultural tensions with governance, external influences, ignorance, and unemployment, among others. Likewise, Ezejuhgu (2021), assess the effect of insecurity on economic development in Nigeria, examines how persistent insecurity challenges such as kidnapping, terrorism, and armed robbery affect economic performance in Nigeria demonstrates that insecurity has significantly hindered economic growth by discouraging investment, distorting production processes, and increasing unemployment. The study concluded that sustainable development cannot be achieved in Nigeria unless the issue of insecurity is adequately addressed

Austin- Egole *et al* (2022) conducted an empirical assessment of insecurity and the socioeconomic living standards of the people of Orlu in the State, Nigeria. from 2018 to 2022, using qualitative methods discovers that insecurity adversely affects the socioeconomic living standards of residents, as people are often forced to remain indoors, leading to business closures and the suspension of social activities. Similar finding is related to the works of Okeya, Frank & Enyindah (2024), on the implications of Insecurity on economic development in Rural States from 2000 to 2015, discovers that insecurity negatively impacted economic growth in river states, leading to the relocation

of businesses, increased tax evasion, and a decline in revenue generation. Also, Abiodun, Magaji & Ismail (2025) confirms that there exists a strong negative impact between insecurity and economic growth as it results to reduced investment, decline in productivity and rise in economic uncertainty, thereby limiting economic development.

Manufacturing Output and Living Standards

Additionally, looking at the relationship between Manufacturing sector and living standard or GDP per capita, there are various studies that have been conducted. Oburota, Eke & Adeyemi (2024) analysed the existing nexus between the manufacturing sector and economic growth in Nigeria. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model on time series data spanning from 1990 to 2023. the findings showed that the manufacturing sector positively impacts economic growth in Nigeria, both in the short and long run. This finding aligns with the works of Afolabi & Laseinde (2019), on manufacturing sector performance and economic Growth in Nigeria using same model and data from 1981 to 2016 discovered, both short- and long-run relationships among the variables, showing that manufacturing capacity utilisation positively influenced real GDP, while government investment expenditure had a negative effect on real GDP. Conversely, money supply was found to have a positive effect on real GDP. The results also revealed a unidirectional causality running from real GDP to other independent variables.

In another study by Chukwu *et al.* (2022) on the nexus between the manufacturing sector and the economic development of Nigeria from 1999 to 2021, using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model reveals that the manufacturing sector has a statistically significant effect on the Human Development Index (HDI) in Nigeria. Anugworn (2024), in their study's findings on "Manufacturing Subsector and Economic Growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022 while applying linear regression model alongside the Error Correction Model (ECM) shows that cement production, pulp and paper production, and beverages and tobacco manufacturing contribute positively but insignificantly to economic growth. Conversely, chemical and pharmaceutical productions were found to contribute negatively, though insignificantly, to economic growth.

Similarly, in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cero *et al* (2021) examines the impact of specific performance indicators of the manufacturing industry on the economic development of during the pre-COVID-19 period, covering a period of five years -2015 - 2019 using multiple regression analysis found that the processing industry contributes positively to the economic development of both countries. In a similar vein, Peter, Olushola & Ac-Ogbonna (2024) investigated the relationship between manufacturing sector output and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2021 using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, discovers the existence of both short- and long-run relationships between the manufacturing sector's output and economic performance. However, while the long-run effect was negative but statistically insignificant, the short-run effect was positive and significant.

Population Growth and Living Standards

On the relationship between Population and living standard or GDP per capita, there are quite a lot of literatures that has been carried out. In Nigeria, Onah (2022) investigated the implications of population growth on the quality of life of city dwellers in Enugu, using qualitative method discovers that bad governance, emigration for greener pastures, increasing unemployment, poverty, and lack of positive development are all linked to the poor quality of life among city dwellers in Nigeria. Likewise, the increase in baby mothers was identified as an essential cause of the soaring population in the country. This finding is consistent with Furuoka & Munir (2014), investigated the relationship between population growth and per capita GDP across 117 countries, indicated a significant negative relationship between population growth and per capita GDP, particularly for countries with low levels of human development.

Also, Aye-Agele & Abubakar (2022) examined population growth and living standards in the Nigerian Economy covering the period from 1961 to 2019 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, trend analysis, confirmed the existence of a long-run relationship between population growth and standard of living in Nigeria, while the Error Correction Model (ECM) indicated a 103% speed of divergence from long-run to short-run equilibrium. The trend analysis further revealed that per capita income growth trended negatively below population growth during several years under review. Omolua & Koru (2024) in their study confirms that population growth and poverty has negatively impacted on the standard of living of Nigerians.

Contrarily, Akinola (2021) analysed the impact of population on economic growth in Nigeria using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method for data spanning from 1994 to 2020, discovered a positive relationship between economic growth, population growth, the food production index, and the human development index. Conversely, a negative relationship was observed between economic growth and fossil fuel consumption. The Granger causality test indicated a unidirectional relationship running from population growth to economic growth.

More so, Khusanaliev (2023) investigated the dynamic relationship between population growth and economic development, particularly focusing on its effect on human development outcomes. from 2012–2021 discovers that rapid population growth is closely linked to developmental trials and can slow down progress if unchecked. The conclusion stresses that while population growth provides labour force advantages, it becomes a barrier when it surpasses resource availability, thereby requiring strategic economic policies. This aligns with Teperek (2025), reveals that the smallest economies vary across different levels of economic development low, lower-middle, upper-middle, and high income. Importantly, the study identifies a significant correlation between urbanisation and economic development, showing that higher proportions of urban dwellers are generally linked with greater levels of economic progress.

On the other hand, Nkwatoh & Nathaniel (2018), examines the effect of insecurity on economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data from 2009 to 2016 and Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, which reveals that economic growth and investment

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activities tended to increase during periods of insecurity, while unemployment declines. This implies that insecurity threaten economic activities however has no negative significant effect on economic growth. Likewise, Omine (2018) concluded that insecurity negatively affects economic growth by drying out investment, increases unemployment and shrinks government revenue.

Aghaulor (2020) examined growth impact of insecurity on the Nigerian Economy using data from 1981 to 2017 and employing econometric tools discovers that variables such as the Terrorism Index, Adult Illiteracy Rate, and Corruption Perception Index have a direct relationship with life expectancy and GDP in the long run, while the Discomfort Index exhibited an inverse relationship with GDP in the long run.

Agogbua, Mgbatogu & Nzewi,(2022) conducted a study investigating the relationship between insecurity and Nigeria’s economic growth and development from 2009 to 2022. The data were systematically divided into two phases: the pre-high insecurity period (2009–2015) and the high insecurity period (2016–2022), discovers that insecurity hampers business activities and disrupts socioeconomic stability, it does not have a statistically significant influence on overall economic growth and development in Nigeria.

Gaps in the Literature

However, a review from the previous studies, a larger proportion of the literature examines the individual relationship between corruption, insecurity, manufacturing output and population growth on macroeconomic indicators, (i.e., Grundler & Potrafke, 2019; Odi, 2014; Lawan *et al* 2023; Enakhe, 2018; Ezeiuhou, 2021; Agogbua, Mgbatogu & Nzewi, 2022) a critical vacuum exists in examining its combined impact of these challenges on the living standards of Nigerians. By focusing on living standards only few studies have been conducted (Onov, 2024; Austin-Egoole *et al* 2022) but they are state specific and qualitative in nature; thus, creating a country specific and methodological gap as this study is to provide quantitative analysis as relates to National-Nigeria context.

Methodology

Quantitative method was employed using annual time series data from 1994– 2024. Key variables employed include GDP per capita, Manufacturing output, Corruption, Insecurity and population growth. The data were obtained as follows: GDP per capita, manufacturing output and population growth were obtained from World Bank, Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics and Statistica databases whereas data on corruption and insecurity were sourced from Transparency international and fund for peace database. To analyse the data, econometric tools such as unit root, ARDL model and other post estimation test was employed. Furthermore, the present study adapted the model from the works of Odi (2014) which examines the impact of corruption on Economic Growth in Nigeria: The initial model is presented as thus

$$GDP = f(COR)$$

Eq 3.1

GDP = Gross domestic product (economic growth); COR = Corruption

Modifying equation 3.1, the new model is expressed in equation 3.2

$$LS = f(COPI, INSI, MANO, POPG)$$

Eq 3.2

$$GDPPI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 COPI + \beta_2 INSI + \beta_3 MANO + \beta_4 POPG + \mu_1$$

Eq 3.3

Where:

LS: Standard of living; *COPI*: Corruption; *INSI*: Insecurity; *MANO*: Manufacturing Output; *POPG*: Population Growth

Re-specifying equation (3.3), into the generalised ARDL Model as in Eq 3.4, it is therefore written as thus

The generalized ARDL model can be specified as thus;

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i \Delta X_{t-1} + \theta_1 Y_{t-1} + \theta_2 X_{t-1} + \mu_t$$

Eq3.4

Equation 3.4 can be re-written as thus:

$$\Delta LS_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta LS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{1i} \Delta COPI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{2i} \Delta INSI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{3i} \Delta MANO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{4i} \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \theta_1 COPI_{t-1} + \theta_2 INSI_{t-1} + \theta_3 MANO_{t-1} + \theta_4 POPG_{t-1} + \mu_t$$

Eq3.5

Where:

ΔLS_t : The dependent variable representing Standard of Living at time t ; β_0 : Intercept term; β_i : Coefficients for the lagged differences of LS; $\lambda_{1i} \lambda_{2i} \lambda_{3i} \lambda_{4i}$: Coefficient for the lagged differences for the independent variables,

$\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4$: Coefficient for the lagged levels of the independent variables; μ_t : Error term at time t .

The long run coefficient of the ARDL model is specify as follows:

$$LS_t = \theta_0 + \theta_1 COPI_t + \theta_2 INSI_t + \theta_3 MANO_t + \theta_4 POPG_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Eq3.6

Where:

θ_0 : Intercept Term; $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4$: Long run coefficients for *COPI*, *INSI*, *MANO* and *POPG*; ε_t : Residual term representing deviations from the long run equilibrium.

Subsequently, after obtaining the long run coefficient of the parameters, the short run coefficient was estimated by adopting the ECM-ARDL short run approach which is given as:

$$\Delta LS_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta LS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{1i} \Delta COPI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{2i} \Delta INSI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{3i} \Delta MANO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_{4i} \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \gamma ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Eq3.7

Where: ECT_{t-1} : Error correction term and γ : The speed of adjustment.

Table 1: Variable Description and Measurement

This sub-section provides a clarification of the variables that form the model, the unit of their measurement, how was it used and the expected relationship with the dependent variable while justifying it with previous studies so as to make interpretation easier.

Variables	Symbols	Nature/ Measurements	Apriori Expectation	Source
Corruption	COPI	It is independent variable. measured using Corruption Perception Index. The CPI used which assumes values ranges 100 (Very clean) to 0	Positive (+)	Grundler & Potrafke (2019); Transparency International (2022)

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Insecurity	INSI	(highly corrupt). The variable is an independent variable which is measured using security threat index. The index ranges between 0 (low) to 10 (high).	Negative (-)	Peace Fund (2022)
Population growth	POPG	It is independent variable. measured in percentages (%)	Positive (+)	World Bank (2023)
Manufacturing Output	MANO	The variable is an independent variable measured in monetary unit-USD Dollars	Positive (+)	World Bank (2023)
Living Standard	LS	It is a dependent variable. which is proxied by Gross Domestic Product Per Capita, measured in monetary unit-USD Dollars		World Bank (2023)

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

Results and Discussion

Pre-Estimation Test: Unit root test particularly the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) was conducted to determine the stationarity of the series as well as the lag selection criterion to as to obtain the optimal lag.

Unit Root Test

Table 2: Unit Root Test

Variable	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test		Order of Integration	Remarks
	Level	First Difference		
COPI	-3.4897 (0.015)	-3.2959 (0.026)	I (0)	Stationary
INSI	-1.1975 (0.662)	-5.354 (0.000)	1(I)	Stationary
POPG	-0.8703 (0.780)	-4.121 (0.016)	1(I)	Stationary
MANO	-2.245 (0.157)	-3.075 (0.040)	1(I)	Stationary
LS	-1.5995 (0.470)	-3.998 (0.004)	1(I)	Stationary

Source: eViews 10

Table 2 shows that Corruption (COPI) is stationary at level I(0) whereas Insecurity (INSI), Population growth (POPG), Manufacturing output (MANO) and Standard of Living (LS) are stationary at their first difference I(1) at 5.0 per cent level of significance. This implies that there is a mixture of order of integration which necessitate the application of Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model.

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

This is conducted in order to determine the optimal number lags (past year) to include in the model in order to capture the dynamic relationship that exist among the variables

Table 3: Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-442.03	NA	16859045	30.82965	31.06539	30.90348
1	-324.37	186.6377*	29144.47*	24.43910*	25.85355*	24.88209*
2	-306.82	21.77862	57720.44	24.95332	27.54646	25.76546

Source: eViews 10

From Table 3, Lag 1 is the selected lag order which corresponds with the asterisk on the criterion. The values of these criteria are the lowest among the option, thereby indicating a better fit. This decision of lag 1 aligns with the rule of thumb that, the criterion with the lowest minimum value is adequate (Asteriou & Hall, 2011).

ARDL Bound Test for Co-integration

Table 4: ARDL Bound Test for Cointegration Test Results

Test Statistic	Value	Signif	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	2.456	10%	2.525	3.56
K	4	5%	3.058	4.22
		1%	4.28	5.84

Source: eViews 10

Table 4 reveals that that there is no long relationship between the series. This is because the value of F-statistic (2.456) is less than the lower (3.058) and upper (4.22) critical bounds limits at 5% significance level. By this outcome, only the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) short run estimate was conducted.

ARDL Estimates

Table 5: ARDL Short run Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(COPI)	21.78106	7.734462	2.816106	0.0107**
D(INSI)	23.74564	14.64426	1.621497	0.1206
D(MANO)	30.64548	2.757435	11.11376	0.0000**
D(POPG)	-481.9504	920.8947	-0.52335	0.6065
CointEq(-1)*	-0.355197	0.082756	-4.29212	0.0004**
R-squared	0.908565			
Adjusted R-squared	0.893935			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.472762			

Source: EViews 10

**** 5% level of significance**

Table 5 reveals the ARDL short run estimates. The variable COPI (corruption perception index) has a positive coefficient of 21.78 with a p-value of 0.011 which is statistically significant at 5 percent. This means that an increase in corruption (better corruption perception index score), it leads to a rise in the standard of living of Nigerians (LS) by

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USD21.78 in the short run. By implication, it implies that by having a better score of corruption on the corruption perception index, it means public resources are better use for developmental purpose rather than diverting it for personal gains. Also, fiscal leakages are minimised, thereby attracting greater investment in real sectors such as infrastructure, healthcare, industrial development, thereby addressing the structural deficiencies that constraint output. By so doing, market efficiency is improved, better business environment is achieved for private sector participation, thus leading to innovation and industrial expansion. On the aggregate, these translate to an increase in production leading to higher per capita income, thereby resulting to an increase in the level of standard of living of Nigerians. This outcome corroborates with the institutional theory, aligns further with *apriori* expectations and previous studies of Onakoya & Folorunsho (2015) and Akmal *et al* (2024), who concluded that a reduction in corruption or having higher corruption perception index leads to enhanced institutional performances, boast economic efficiency and promotes sustainable economic growth and welfare.

Insecurity (INSI) proxied by Nigeria security threat index and Population growth (POPG) has a positive (30.65) and negative (-481.95) coefficient respectively but they are not statistically significant because their respective p-values are greater than 5 per cent. This implies that there is no reliable short run effect of these variables on the standard of living Nigerians (LS). Manufacturing out (MANO) possessed a positive coefficient and is statistically significant. It is the strongest short run drivers among the variables. This implies that a unit increase in MANO leads to an increase in PCIC by USD30.65. By this outcome, it implies that as manufacturing sector contributes to income growth, productivity enhancement and over all ensures economic stability. This positive relationship between the duo by extension implies that as manufacturing output increases, the Nigerian economy records a spillover effect through an improved industrial capacity utilisation, job creation and invariably increased wages. This will result to increase in supply, thus stabilising prices of goods and ensuring affordability by households. By so doing, it gives households the opportunities to have access to varieties of consumer products and the resulting increase in the real purchasing power translate into improve standard of living by households. In addition, the increase in manufacturing sector performance could trigger backward and forwards linkages with other sectors like agriculture, trade and service sectors, thereby spurring an inclusive growth and sustainable economic development. This outcome is consistent with *apriori* expectations, the endogenous growth theory and the works of Cero *et al* (2021); Chukwu *et al* (2022); Peter, Olushola & Ac-Ogbonna (2024) and Anugworn (2024), who concluded that manufacturing output positively influences national income, employment and household welfare.

More so, the ContEq (-1) has a coefficient of -0.355 and is statistically significant. This outcome means that LS corrects back to its long run equilibrium after a short run shock by 35%. Furthermore, on the model, goodness of fit, R^2 adjusted is approximately 90% which means that a large proportion of PCIC is been explained by the independent variables (COPI, MANO, INSI and POPG). The DW statistics of 2.47 reveals that there is no fist order autocreation as buttressed by Field (2009) that DW statistic under 1 or more than 3 create a cause for concern.

Post Estimation Test

Table 6: Diagnostic Results

Test Type	Statistic/P-value
Normality (Jarque-Bera)	1.316 [0.517]
Heteroscedasticity $\chi^2(2)$	0.626 [0.761]
Serial Correlation $\chi^2(2)$:	3.355 [0.082]

Source: EViews 10 Output

Table 4.5 reveals the post estimation test conducted for the model, which confirms that it is normal, homoscedastic, free from serial-correlation, and not mis specified because their respective p-values are greater than 5 per cent.

Stability Test

The model stability test such as CUSUM and CUSUM of square test was conducted to ascertain whether the model is stable or not as displayed in Figure 4.1 and 4.2 respectively

Figure 1: CUSUM Test

Figure 2: CUSUM of Squares

Source: Eviews 10 Output

Figure 1 and 2 depicts that the model is stable. This is because CUSUM plots aligns with the rule of thumb that it must lies within both the lower and upper bounds and if otherwise, the model is not stable (Tang & Lean, 2007).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study concludes the corruption and manufacturing output has a significant impact on the standards of living of Nigerians whereas population growth and insecurity exert minimal effect in the short run. Specifically, lower corruption levels enhance better resource allocation, ensures institutional efficiency and productivity, thereby result to a higher per capita income. Meanwhile, increased in manufacturing output leads to employment and stabilises consumer prices, thus enhancing household

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welfare. However, increasing population and insecurity undermines long term gains in Nigeria if not properly managed with an all-inclusive policy. Consequently, the study offers the following recommendations for possible implementation:

1. There is need for the Nigerian Government at all levels to strengthened its anti-corruption drive by ensuring transparency in its fiscal operations, empowering oversight agencies and enforcing accountability across MDAs to enhance resource efficiency and improve public welfare.
2. There is need to revitalise the manufacturing sector by designing policies that will encourage local production by ensuring stable power supply, encouraging private-public partnership, investing in infrastructure and ensuring access to credit and this will by extension result to increase in output, create employment and ensuring sustainable income growth.
3. There is need for the government at all levels to design strategies to focus on community-based security intelligence, empowering youth and ensuring rural development
4. There is need to manage the population growth and encouraging family planning so that the increased population aligns with the country economic capacity.

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